

**THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH
IN SOUTH SUDAN**

BY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this research project, which is titled "The impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan", is my original work and has never been presented to any university or higher learning institution for an academic award.

Signature :.....Date:.....

APPROVAL

This is to affirm that this research project has been under my supervision and is now ready for submission to the University of Juba with my approval.

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Principal, Graduate College

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DEDICATION

This beautiful work is dedicated to my beloved parents, more specifically my mother Achol Riak, for her special love, care, advice, encouragement, and support, which helped me overcome this desperate life. May Almighty God continue to shower her with good health.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CES	Central Equatoria State
COVID	Corona Virus Disease
CPA	Comprehensive Peace Agreement
FAO	Food Agricultural Organization
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HDI	Human Development Index
IMF	International Monetary Fund
MoFEP	Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning
NBS:	National Bureau of Statistics
NRA	National Revenue Authority
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PFM	Public Financial Managements
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
SSD	South Sudan
UN	United Nations
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
WB	World Bank
WHO	World Health Organization

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ABSTRACT

The study seeks to assess the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. The study will be guided by two specific objectives, which include analyzing the relationship between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth and identifying the causes and effects of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. The study uses a descriptive research design employing a mixed research design where primary and secondary data will be used.

The study used questionnaires as tools for data collection; these were both open- and closed-ended. Existing studies on the relationship between public expenditure and economic growth have shown conflicting results over time; this means that there is no clear explanation for this relationship. This study therefore examined the relationship and dynamic interactions between the composition of public expenditures and economic growth in South Sudan. Gross domestic product (GDP per capita) was used as a proxy for economic growth in the study. The study used a regression model for panel data to analyze the data. Random effect was found to be the efficient model after Friedman's test results; panel unit root tests.

The study used secondary data. The findings showed that public expenditure on infrastructure, the productive sector, and security is a positive determinant of economic growth, while government expenditure on the social services sector is found to have a negative impact on economic growth. The study therefore recommended, among others, that there should be effective channeling of public funds to sectors that support growth.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This part of the study involves the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the research objectives, the research questions, the purpose of the study, the limitation of the study, the scope and delimitation, the justification of the study, and the operational definition of key words in the research.

1.1 Background of the study

The correlation between government expenditure and economic growth has continued to generate a series of debates in the economic literature. There are two main theories that explain the long-run relationship between the two variables: Wagner's law and the Keynesian hypothesis. These two theories observe the practical relationship between two variables from different perspectives. Wagner's law considers public expenditure an endogenous factor that is driven by national income (Ufatah, 2010).

Under the overarching theme of "Consolidate Peace, Stabilize the Economy," the Revised National Development Strategy (R-NDS) 2021–2024 expresses national aspirations to transition from dependence on humanitarian aid to a development path using the humanitarian, development, and peace nexus approach and has adopted a comprehensive implementation framework anchored on collaboration with development partners (RSS, 2008). The R-NDS draws lessons from experiences in the implementation of the country's past development plans and strategies and expounds on prevailing opportunities to ensure effective implementation of the plan (Riomero, 2007).

Building on its track record of supporting development planning in the country, UNDP supported its review, ensuring that it is aligned with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This alignment ensures that the R-NDS offers strategic direction to the country's development agenda and conforms to international standards (Shenggen, 2019).

Amid the conflict and determined to stay the course on the development agenda, the GRSS and its partners designed and launched the 2018–2021 National Development Strategy (NDS) in June

2018. Recognizing the devastating humanitarian impact of the 2016–17 civil war, the NDS aimed to "consolidate peace and stabilize the economy". It focused on four clusters: governance, economics, social services, and cross-cutting. At the heart of the NDS was meeting the people of South Sudan's aspirations to feel safe, enjoy stable prices, and have access to basic services. Implementation of the NDS was overshadowed by peace negotiations, which led to the signing of the Revitalized Agreement on the Resolution of the Conflict in South Sudan (R-ARCSS) in September (GRSS, 2022).

Developing a strategy is, by necessity, a participatory process. The NDS 2018–2021 was compromised by limited participation due to the conflict situation prevailing in the country at the time of its formulation (UNDP, 2022). Unlike the NDS 2018–2021, this R-NDS benefited from several consultative processes. The Ministry of Finance and Planning constituted an NDS Steering Committee, a Secretariat, and reinvigorated sector working groups to lead consultations and produce the R-NDS. The Steering Committee endorsed a set of consultation processes organized into five categories: first, national consultations with citizens and development partners; second, fragility assessment; third, a review of policies for the integration of the SDGs in the NDS; fourth, gender analysis and mainstreaming; and fifth, a development finance assessment and road map for an integrated national financing framework. The results of these processes informed the content and implementation strategy of this R-NDS

Include a paragraph of two regarding R-NDS vis a vis your study

In contrast to it, the Keynesian hypothesis considers public expenditure as an exogenous variable that influences economic growth. Keynesian views establish the direction of causality as being from public expenditures to economic growth. Knowledge of the precise direction of causality has important policy implications. Keynesians also view public expenditure as an important policy variable, as was experienced during the Great Depression of the 1930s in the industrialized Western world. Government activity may directly or indirectly increase total output through its interaction with the private sector (Tang, 2005).

Lin (2019) outlines some important ways in which the government can increase growth. These include the provision of public goods and infrastructure, social services, and targeted

interventions (such as export subsidies). Economic growth is an essential ingredient for sustainable development. Economic growth brings about a better standard of living for the people, and this is most often brought about by improvements in the availability of infrastructure, access to food, health, housing, and education (Lin, 2007).

These sectors are very important in stimulating the economic activities as well as addressing the nation's human development and thereby bringing about sustainable development. Economic growth also can be used as a gauge to evaluate the performance of the economic development of a country. Economic growth is closely related to the economic situation in the long term and reflects the occurrence of expansion in the economy because of government expenditure. Rapid economic growth would be vital to increase income and job opportunities for the people. To enable economic growth to be maintained at a high level, one of the important factors that needs to be enhanced is government expenditure. Government expenditure is one of the important tools that contribute to the economic growth of a nation, including South Sudan. Government expenditure includes the allocation provided by the government to carry out various government projects with a desire to enhance (GRSS, 2022).

Public expenditure policies aim at increasing public expenditure productivity, though not sufficient, are desirable (Egbetunde and Fasanya, 2015). Government activity may directly or indirectly increase total output through its interaction with the private sector. Economic growth is closely related to the economic situation in the long term and reflects the occurrence of expansion in economy because of government expenditure. Rapid economic growth would be vital to increase income and job opportunities for the people. To enable economic growth to be maintained at a high-level, one of the important factors which need to be enhanced is government expenditure (Levine and Renelt, 2007).

1.2 Motivation

South Sudan is an oil-producing country with sufficient income and an abundance of economic potential that placed it on the list of middle-income countries in the world. It continued to record positive current account balances over years with a high GDP per capita income compared to its neighbors. Budgets are on the increase every year, with budget deficits financed through

borrowing from the WB, IMF, and other multilateral financial institutions, with the debt going as high as over the 50% GDP threshold (Bank, World Development Report, 2006).

In addition, development assistance is continually offered by the UN and its development partners, including the UNDP, United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), World Health Organization (WHO), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), and other multilateral institutions and development partners (South Sudan National Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

However, despite loans and assistance, and above all, the availability of oil and non-oil revenues, the country remains below the list of the poorest countries in the world. According to the South Sudan National Bureau of Statistics (2018) With a 70% illiteracy rate and more than 80% of the population living below the poverty line, the Human Development Index (HDI) is less than 0.5%, with poor infrastructure development, a high unemployment rate, a high mortality rate, the absence of an internal market, and other development indicators. (South Sudan National Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

This study is therefore intended to develop an analytical framework for determining relationships between various government expenditure components and economic growth. This is with a view to assisting the policymakers in having empirical knowledge of determining the economic components of the allocation of public funds and avoiding intuition in making expenditure decisions, which mostly lead to disastrous economic consequences. This study has never been done in South Sudan. Thus, it is very important to look at trends, levels, and composition of public expenditures, being aware of the fact that optimally directing these expenditures that have a positive relation with economic growth, eliminating expenses that have a negative relation, and separating the neutral ones are necessary.

1.3 Statement of the problem

South Sudan has been running its economy since the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) was signed in 2005. Public expenditures have been rising. In the early years of the CPA, between 2006 and 2008, capital expenditures were above 25% of the total, the government was able to spend a reasonable share of its resources on capital, but after 2008, the capital share started

gradually declining, reaching below 20% in 2010 and 2011, and 17% in the first 6 months of 2012 (South Sudan National Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

Capital expenditure decreased only in relative terms. In USD equivalent, capital expenditure decreased in 2009, in correspondence with a sharp decrease in oil revenue due to falling oil prices, and then increased gradually, but less than current expenditure. The budgeted amounts for capital expenditures show an even more dramatic decline in the last three budgets, going from 17% in the FY2011–2012 budget to 6% in the FY2012–2013 budget, demonstrating how capital expenditures bore the brunt of the fiscal austerity adjustment. In fact, capital expenditures have been cut by 80% in the FY2012/2013 budget, compared to 22% for salaries and 9% for transfers, and other expenditures have been cut by 47%. This is largely expected, as it is easier to cut investment spending than to reduce salary payments in the face of temporary revenue shortfalls (South Sudan Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, 2016).

The declining share of capital expenditures from 2009 to 2011 was actually accompanied also by a reduction in the share of the wage bill (the wage bill increased, but at a slower pace than overall expenditures, hence lowering its share). However, because of their rigidity, the share of wages and salaries went up again in the context of the last austerity budget, as they are difficult to cut. This seems to indicate that the level of the wage bill, which is on the very high side by international standards, needs to be addressed structurally to allow for a more investment- and growth-oriented budget in the years to come (South Sudan Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, 2016).

Operating expenditures are high, at around 40 percent of total expenditure, and they have been growing in the last few years. It will be important to analyze and, in some cases, reclassify operating expenditures, which often include many wage and salary elements and transfers. It may also be necessary to identify areas for cost savings and rationalization. (South Sudan Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, 2016).

Sadly, two years after independence, South Sudan's leaders decided to squander their country's future and far too many lives in a political power struggle (UNOCHA 2020)

The lack of studies on the relationship between government expenditure components and economic growth in the newly independent, fragile, and conflict-ridden state of South Sudan motivated this study.

1.4. Objectives of the study

The main objective is to assess the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan.

1.4.1 Specific objectives

1. To analyze the relationship between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth in South Sudan.
2. To identify the causes and effects of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan.
3. To generate information that will be used by the policy makers in R-NDS and other researchers.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth in South Sudan?
2. What are the causes and effects of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan?

1.6 Purpose of the Study

The aims of this quantitative, non-experimental research design are to examine the potential impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. And the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth to help policymakers formulate programs on public expenditure. Moreover, the study will examine the impact of government expenditure on economic growth to derive ways forward in policy recommendations in order to address economic instability in South Sudan.

1.7 Limitations of the Study

This research attempted to measure the impact of selected public expenditures on determinants of economic growth. Due to limited information, the searcher relies on data from the World Bank, UNDP Report, and World Development Indicators (WDI). While the data and inputs are authentic, there is a risk of these inputs being diluted due to some factors:

- The major limitation of this study is the non-availability of data for some expenditure variables, of which some expenditure variables are dropped for the study.
- Another major limitation is the duration of study and budgetary or financial constraints.
- This study is limited to Juba City only due to insecurity factors in other states.
- The study will also be limited by the insecurity situation in South Sudan.

1.8 Scope and delimitation of the study

The study was conducted in the Republic of South Sudan, Juba City and it was limited to the National Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning's Department of Expenditures, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and NRA annual data from 2011–2022.

1.9 Justification, significance, and rationale of the study

Realizing the importance and contribution of public expenditure in economic growth, this study captures the effect of selected expenditures on selected variables of the economies of the Republic of South Sudan. This research is significant to the general public, researchers, ministries, foreign investors, and governments in different ways:

- Policy and decision-makers, at different levels (national, regional, and local) of public expenditure management as well as informing allocation of resources for implementing R-NDS
- Future researchers working on public expenditure and investment

1.11 Organization of the study

The study is organized into five chapters. The first chapter, which is an introductory chapter, consists of a general introduction, the background to the study, a statement of the problem, research objectives, research questions, the purpose of the study, the limitations of the study, the scope and delimitation of the study, and a study and operational definition of a keyword used in the research. Chapter two deals with a literature review, including both theoretical and empirical literature on public expenditure and economic growth based on previous scholars work on the topics and the gap in the study, while chapter three discusses the methodology that will be used to collect and analyze the data. Moreover, chapter four will discuss the research findings and presentation of results. The study will conclude with Chapter 5, which will include the summary, conclusions, and policy recommendations to the policy makers in South Sudan

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter defines the key terms that will be used in the study and present a literature review and theoretical framework on the impact of government expenditure on economic growth.

Economic Growth: Economic growth is an increase in the production of economic goods and services in one period of time compared with a previous period. It can be measured in nominal or real (adjusted to remove inflation) terms (Baker, 1999).

Government Expenditure: Government spending refers to money spent by the public sector on the acquisition of goods and provision of services such as education, healthcare, social protection, and defense (Lansbury, 2014).

Investment Expenditure: Investment expenditure concerns capital operations. It includes: the repayment of loans; loans and advances granted by the authority; direct investment expenditure (equipment and real estate acquisitions, new work, major repairs) (Lansbury, 2014).

Debt service: Total debt service is the sum of principal repayments and interest actually paid in currency, goods, or services on long-term debt, interest paid on short-term debt, and repayments (repurchases and charges) to the IMF. Total debt service to exports of goods, services, and primary income.

Debt and transfers: A transfer payment is a payment of money, usually from the government, for which there are no goods or services exchanged (World Economic Forum, 2011).

Population: This term applies to the totality of all units of interest in a study or investigation at a given time in a given area (Lansbury, 2014).

Human capital is the stock of competencies, knowledge, and social and personality attributes, including creativity, embodied in the ability to perform labor so as to produce economic goods (Lansbury, 2014).

Disaggregated Data: The separation of an aggregate body of data into its component parts to uncover patterns, trends, and other important information (Lansbury, 2014).

Openness: exports of goods and services (% of GDP) plus imports of goods and services (% of GDP) (World Bank, 2006).

Panel data: data that combines the time series with cross-sectional variation in the analysis of determinants of economic growth (Usman, 2007)

2.1 Theoretical framework

2.1.1 The Keynesian theory

The Keynesian model indicates that during a recession, a policy of budgetary expansion should be undertaken to increase aggregate demand in the economy, thus boosting the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Keynes regards public expenditures as an exogenous factor that can be utilized as a policy instrument to promote economic growth. According to Keynesian thought, public expenditure can contribute positively to economic growth. Hence, an increase in government consumption is likely to lead to an increase in employment, profitability, and investment through multiplier effects on aggregate demand. As a result, government expenditure augments aggregate demand, which provokes an increased output depending on expenditure multipliers. In economic theory, it appears as the Harrod-Domar Keynesian Theory of Growth, or simply, the Harrod-Domar Growth Model. A mathematical equation of this model, $y = f(k, s)$, shows the existence of a direct relationship between savings and the rate of economic growth (Keynes H. , 1789).

2.1.2 The Big Push Theory

The Big Push Theory has been presented by Paul Rosenstein Rodan. The idea behind this theory is that a big push or a big and comprehensive investment package can be helpful for economic development. In other words, a certain minimum amount of resources must be devoted to developmental programs if their success is required (Rodan, 1943).

The theory behind the model emphasizes that underdeveloped countries require large amounts of investment to embark on the path of economic development from their present state of backwardness. As some ground speed is required for the aircraft to become airborne, in the same way, a certain critical amount of resources must be allocated for development activities. This theory is of the view that through bit by bit allocation, no economy can move on the path of economic development; rather, a specific amount of investment is considered something necessary for economic development. Therefore, if so many mutually supporting industries that depend on each other are started, the economies of scale will be reaped. Such external economies, which are attained through specific amounts of investment, will be helpful for economic development.

2.1.3 Peacock and Wiseman's Political Constraint Theory

Wiseman and Peacock revealed in their study of public expenditure in the UK for the period 1890–1955, that public expenditure does not increase in a smooth and continuous manner but in jerks or steps like fashion. At times, some social or other disturbance takes place, creating a need for increased public expenditures that the existing public revenue cannot meet. While earlier, due to an insufficient demand for public expenditure, the revenue constraint was dominating and restraining an expansion in public expenditure, now, under changed requirements, such a restraint gives way. They founded their analyses on a political theory of public determination, namely that governments like to spend more money and citizens do not like to pay taxes, and that governments need to pay some attention to the wishes of their citizens. The duo saw taxation as setting a constraint on government expenditure. As the economy and thus incomes grew, tax revenue at a constant tax rate would rise, thereby enabling public expenditure to show a gradual upward trend, even though within the economy there might be a divergence between what people regarded as the desirable level of public expenditure and the desirable level of taxation. During periods of social upheaval, however, this gradual upward trend in public expenditure would be disturbed (Peacock and Wiseman, 1955).

The public expenditure increases, making the inadequacy of the present revenue quite clear to everyone. The movement from the older level of expenditure and taxation to a new and higher level is the displacement effect. The inadequacy of the revenue as compared with the required public expenditure creates an inspection effect. The government and the people review the revenue position and the need to find a solution to the important problems that have come up and agree to the required adjustments to finance the increased expenditure (Muthui, 2013).

They attain a new level of tax tolerance. They are now ready to tolerate a greater burden of taxation, and as a result, the general level of expenditure and revenue goes up. In this way, public expenditure and revenue get stabilized at a new level until another disturbance occurs to cause a displacement effect. Thus, each major disturbance leads to the government assuming a larger proportion of total national activity. In other words, there is a concentration effect. The concentration effect also refers to the apparent tendency for central government economic activity to grow faster than that of the state and local governments.

2.2 Empirical Literature

The empirical review primarily focused on the impact of public expenditure on economic growth in developing countries.

2.2.1 Public expenditure and economic growth

Infrastructure is key to delivering several essential services and plays a central role in achieving a nation's Sustainable Development Goals. However, infrastructure either directly or indirectly influences the attainment of all of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UNDP, 2017).

Developing countries face significant infrastructure needs if they are to deliver on the 2030 policy agenda (Bank, Service Trade and Development: the experience of African Countries, 2007). There have been few rigorous attempts to quantify these spending needs, and until recently most of them were based on high-level cross-country panel econometric studies were limited in scope to individual regions or sectors (Garmendia, 2009).

Good infrastructure does not enhance a country's economic potential. Good transport infrastructure can enhance labor mobility, for example, while good energy infrastructure can deliver low-cost power to the fuel industry. When it comes to macroeconomic health, however, large numbers of politicians and economists now make the case that a lot more state-led infrastructure investment is needed 'to boost growth (McDonnell, 2013).

There tend to be two separate arguments for this, which are often conflated but should be analyzed distinctly. The first is that infrastructure spending is a useful tool of Keynesian economics. This says that when an economy is in recession or slowing and unemployment is high, government spending to finance and/or build infrastructure can help alleviate unemployment directly and have a strong multiplier effect on the economy more generally. For this reason, some economists advocated for more infrastructure spending in the expectation that Brexit referendum-induced uncertainty would lead to an economic slowdown.

The second is that infrastructure spending can actually enhance the productive potential of the economy improving its supply side. This argument says that greater state-financed investment in infrastructure can boost the productive potential of the economy by greasing the wheels of economic activity in the future.

These two arguments are often made together (Johnson, 2013). But they are really distinct. If one were purely interested in short-term demand management, it does not matter which types of projects are chosen; what matters is reducing unemployment directly and putting resources back to work. One would invest quite differently if you had the maximization of long-run growth as your aim. Having multiple goals in this case demands management and short-run growth maximization, which creates conflict.

Keynesian theory in essence says that in times of recession, good macro negates what we know about good micro. We might oppose wasteful 'make jobs schemes in good times, but in recessions they make perfect sense. Even building roads to nowhere and preparing for fake alien invasions are economically worthwhile (Canning, 2005).

In this regard, advocates for more infrastructure spending argue for more spending to boost the supply side. They point to low interest rates at the moment and say that this is an opportune time for the government to invest in roads, rail, energy, housing, and ports (Keynes, 1978).

In the provision of public goods (which markets would under-provide) and on projects where the rate of return is higher than that delivered on private sector projects, well-targeted infrastructure undertaken according to disciplined cost-benefit analysis can enhance our economic well-being. But given a low interest rate environment that makes investment in both the public and private sectors more cost effective, the real question here is whether infrastructure is better delivered by the public or private sector. Are there vast numbers of worthy projects that simply cannot be delivered by the private sector due to market failures? And does the political process lend itself to making better long-term decisions on infrastructure than markets, such that the marginal rate of return exceeds the opportunity cost of allocating the same resources elsewhere, including to output-stimulating tax cuts (Lansbury, 2014).

An adequate supply of infrastructure services has long been viewed as a key ingredient for economic development, both in the academic literature (Aschauer, 1989) and in the policy debate. Over the last two decades, academic research has devoted considerable effort to theoretical and empirical analyses of the contribution of infrastructure development to growth and productivity. More recently, increasing attention has also been paid to the impact of infrastructure on poverty and inequality (World Bank, 1997). While the empirical literature on these two topics is far from unanimous, on the whole, a consensus has emerged that, under the right conditions, infrastructure development can play a major role in promoting growth and equity and, through both channels, helping reduce poverty.

2.2.2 Production sector expenditure and economic growth

The value of agricultural production is crucial in determining the state of the agricultural sector when compared to other economic sectors (FAO, 1999).

According to the Food and Agricultural Organization the value of agricultural production expresses total agricultural output in monetary terms, whereas in the South Sudan context, the

value of agricultural production is defined by the total production of field crops, horticultural crops, and livestock products valued at average farm-gate prices (FAO, 1995)

The examination of the effect that government expenditure has on public sectors, such as agriculture, has been overlooked in various studies analyzed the effect of government expenditure on the overall economy of South Africa. Despite this, empirical studies on factors that affect the value of agricultural production are very few in South Africa. The present study differs from previous studies since it analyzes the effect of government expenditure on the sectoral level (the agricultural sector) rather than the whole economy (Odhiambo, 2022).

In addition, the present study is different from most of the literature in South Sudan because it analyzes the effect of selected variables on the value of agricultural output rather than on agricultural production output or agricultural productivity. The importance of this present study is derived from the need to analyze the effect of selected variables on the value of agricultural production with a greater interest in government expenditure on agriculture to further understand the main problem of a fluctuating value of agricultural production. Although this study was conducted In South Africa, global agriculture is diverse, fast-growing, and intertwined through trade (FAO, 2018).

This study is of global interest because the literature reports that South Sudan is developing similarly to other countries (aiming at improving agriculture). Thus, many countries have a common interest in research related to agricultural development. In addition, this present study explores the theme of government expenditure, which is an instrument for agricultural transformation in many countries, thus attracting international interest and readership (Mombayi, 2011).

Examining spending goals for the agricultural sector amid the consensus that the South Sudan agricultural sector is known for job creation, a lot more must be understood in the context of government expenditure in the agricultural sector and agricultural production output (Ernest, 2016). Elista highlighted that understanding the relationship between the value of agricultural production and government expenditure in agriculture helps in determining appropriate policy responses, which ultimately guarantee economic growth. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the effect of government expenditure in agriculture on the value of agricultural production in South Sudan, given that the literature is limited for the period evaluated in this study and that the

findings could highlight possible policy implications, particularly relevant in the context of the growth of the agricultural sector (Elista, 2013).

2.2.3 Public expenditure and economic growth

Social expenditure comprises cash benefits, direct in-kind provision of goods and services, and tax breaks with social purposes. Benefits may be targeted at low-income households, the elderly, disabled, sick, unemployed, or young persons. To be considered "social", programs have to involve either the redistribution of resources across households or compulsory participation. Social benefits are classified as public when the general government (that is, the central, state, and local governments, including social security funds) controls the relevant financial flows. All social benefits not provided by the general government are considered private. Private transfers between households (Jahansen, 1995)

Social Services sector Social services are very important for promoting inclusive growth; they affect development in four ways directly, through effects on national incomes and employment (social services often constitute the majority or main source of income); directly, through effects on the range and quality of social services, such as health and education; and indirectly, through effects on investment climate, including through transport systems, communication services, and energy services. Improvements in health can enhance worker 's productivity by increasing their physical capacities, such as strength and endurance, as well as their mental capacities, such as cognitive functioning and reasoning ability; evidence of this link is increasing at the microeconomic level (Myles, 2007)

There are plausible pathways through which health can influence the pace of income growth at the macroeconomic level also, via its effects on labor market participation, worker productivity, investments in human capital, savings, and population age structure (Jarul, 1936). Moreover, since growth is one of the most important determinants of poverty reduction and since poor health often constrains the productivity of the poor, improvements in health are likely to be particularly beneficial for poverty reduction as well.

2.2.4 Public expenditure on the security sector and economic growth

Security sector expenditure Citizen Security is a key dimension. Crime and violence are increasingly recognized as serious obstacles to the formation of social and human capital, sustainable economic development in Ethiopia, investment, and economic growth (Wabwire, 2006). Increased levels of crime and victimization destroy social capital by fomenting social mistrust, weakening societal unity, and contributing to generalized fear and the erosion of institutions, which are the basic requisites for the collective action needed for development.

Fiscal policy can play an important role in supporting strong, lasting, and equitable growth. In the aftermath of the global financial crisis, potential output in many affected countries declined sharply. Restoring robust growth is essential for addressing the fiscal challenges ahead. Fiscal policy can make an important contribution to lifting potential growth. At the macro level, fiscal policy helps ensure macroeconomic stability, an essential prerequisite for growth; at the micro level, tax and expenditure policies can boost growth by altering work and investment incentives, promoting human capital accumulation, and enhancing total factor productivity. Consistent with earlier studies, fiscal policy is defined to encompass overall budget balance, tax, and expenditure policies (Cullison, 1993)).

Endogenous growth theory provides the analytical framework for studying the effects of fiscal policy on long-run growth. In contrast to neoclassical growth theory, in which policy can only have a transitory effect on growth since long-term growth is driven by exogenous and policy-invariant factors, endogenous growth theory provides a framework to analyze how government policy can affect long-term growth, making it the framework of choice in the public finance literature (Baro, 2014). In practice, however, it is difficult to distinguish between permanent and transitory, but persistent, effects on growth.

This research study draws on the Fund's expertise in providing hands-on advice on fiscal reforms, complemented by a multi-pronged analysis. The Fund has significant expertise and a unique perspective on structural fiscal reforms, including through its extensive technical assistance program. This research also draws from an extensive review of the literature on the topic and several analytical studies. First, the analysis uses a novel technique to estimate the post-reform impact on medium- to long-term growth, which is proxied by 10-year average

growth rates following reforms. Second, a statistical analysis identifies the share of fiscal reform episodes that are followed by growth accelerations within the next 5 years.

Finally, an endogenous growth model simulates the growth impact of several revenue and spending reforms. However, fiscal policy is only one of many factors that drive growth. Despite attempts at isolating the effect of fiscal policy by using three complementary analytical techniques, the results should be interpreted with care given the difficulty in disentangling the impact of fiscal reforms from other factors. The paper differs in important ways from other studies.

First, the coverage in terms of both regions and policies is wider than in other studies where the focus is on a particular country group or region or on specific issues such as the design of tax structures that support growth or the long-term growth effects of public spending (Baily & Courneade, 2015)

Second, the discussion of policy measures is organized around the main growth channels rather than by policy instrument, as is common in the literature. Third, the paper explicitly looks into the equity implications of fiscal policy reforms, an issue that has received less attention in the literature (UNDP, 1993)

Finally, all country studies use a consistent analytical framework to assess the impact of fiscal reforms on potential growth. The growth dividend from fiscal reforms could be substantial. The country studies suggest that there are significant potential gains from fiscal reforms. In advanced countries, per capita growth is estimated to be about 34 percentage points higher following fiscal reforms. The growth dividend could be even higher in emerging markets and LICs. As mentioned above, these results should be interpreted with caution. Other coterminous reforms also played an important role in many cases, and the available analytical tools are limited in the degree to which they can disentangle the effects of fiscal policy from other factors. Simulations of an endogenous growth model, which does isolate the impact of fiscal reforms, show that even a budget-neutral tax reform package aimed at enhancing the efficiency of the tax system may lift long-term growth by as much as 12 percentage point. Shifting the composition of spending toward infrastructure investment could add 14 percentage point. Finally, a statistical analysis

shows that there is a relatively high likelihood that fiscal reforms are followed by growth accelerations.

The effectiveness of growth-friendly fiscal policy is enhanced when reforms reinforce each other and are accompanied by complementary structural reforms. Combining fiscal reforms (e.g., scaling up infrastructure investment while improving the public investment process) increases their effectiveness. Complementary reforms such as liberalizing trade, labor, and product markets can magnify the impact of fiscal reforms by promoting savings, stimulating investment, and unlocking productivity gains.

Policy design and social consensus matter for the successful implementation of reforms. Appropriately designed fiscal reform packages can serve both growth and equity objectives. Social consensus enhances the likelihood of reforms being implemented and sustained. A number of strategies can help foster public support for reforms, including effective communication with stakeholders and the inclusion of compensatory measures for those expected to lose from reforms.

2.3 Critique of Literature

Many studies have aimed at estimating the effects of public expenditure on economic growth. Empirical studies have yielded conflicting results: some support the hypothesis that a rise in the share of public spending is associated with a decline in economic growth. Others have found a positive correlation between economic growth and public spending, and still other studies have found no significant relationship. Results and evidence differ by country or region, analytical method employed, and categorization of public expenditures. In general, studies of the relationship between aggregate public expenditure and economic growth have not yielded robust results, as the results of many are sensitive to small changes in model specification. Levine & Renelt (1992).

Unfortunately, there is no literature available that discusses the effect of public sector expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. The objective of this paper was to analyze the relationship between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth in

South Sudan and to identify the causes and effects of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan.

2.4 Research Gap

Literature on the relationship between public expenditure and economic growth in South Sudan and other fragile, war-affected countries in general is insufficient, as most studies have largely focused on developed countries and stable developing countries. This study aims at filling the gap by using the most recent data to analyze the relationship between public expenditure and economic growth in fragile and underdeveloped South Sudan.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the research design, study population, data collection and procedures, data processing and analysis, and data collection methods and instruments.

3.1 Research Design

This research study was descriptive in nature and used both secondary and primary data. Primary data was used as a source of data and was collected using questionnaires that were both open-ended and closed-ended in nature. The questionnaires were properly checked to ensure they were completely filled out by respondents. The collected data were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for analysis. The data was presented in either frequency tables, charts, or graphs.

3.2 Study Population

The study targeted the population of 44 respondents out of which 33 Male and 5 Female working within the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, the National Revenue Authority, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Central Bank of South Sudan (CBSS) answered and returned questionnaires, It is important to mention their positions and reasons for selecting them

3.3 Data Collection and Procedure

This study used secondary data for the period 2011–2022 as the literature review in chapter two of this research. Data were extracted from the World Bank Index (WBI), the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Central Bank of South Sudan (CBSS), the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning (MoFEP), and the National Revenue Authority (NRA).

A letter seeking to carry out data collection was issued by the head of the Economics Department at the University of Juba, seeking to carry out data collection from the above-listed government agencies. The letter was submitted to the respective government agencies, seeking permission, after Permission was granted, and the researcher agreed on the date to deliver data collection tools, which will involve questionnaires and interview guides. All filled questionnaires were collected and cross-checked for completeness by respondents.

3.4 Data processing and analysis

Panel Unit root test for stationarity (Levin, Lin, and Chu)

The study made use of secondary panel data, and the data were checked for consistency and suitability through a number of statistical measures. Data analysis software, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2.1, was used to analyze the data collected in this study.

Friedman's test

Friedman's test was carried out to choose between the fixed and random effects estimators. Secondly, Friedman's Test for Endogeneity can help us determine whether or not there was some form of omitted variable that biased this regression.

Model Specification

The framework for the study was based on the Keynesian and endogenous growth models. The Keynesian model states that expansion of government expenditure accelerates economic growth. Although endogenous growth models do not assign any important role to government in the growth process, they focus on the components of government expenditure that were productive or unproductive, with the composition of government expenditure exerting more influence than the level of government expenditure.

The Keynesians model economic growth as a function of public expenditure. It defines total public expenditure as a function of the sum of all individual government expenditures in all components.

The modification of the model helped investigate the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. The level and composition of government expenditure were important determinants of growth. Thus, the model expresses economic growth (GDP) as a function of various levels and components of government expenditure that include total infrastructure (FRA), productive (PRO), social services (SOS), and security (SEC). Thus, the growth model is specified as:

$$\text{GDP}=\text{F}(\text{EXFRA},\text{EXPROD},\text{EXSOSE}, \text{EXSEC}.....)(1)$$

Where:

GDP = Gross Domestic Product.

EXFRAS = Expenditure on Infrastructure Sector

EXPROD = Expenditure on Production Sector

EXSOS = Expenditure on Social Services Sector

EXSEC = Expenditure on Security Sector

et = refers to error tem

The above equation is converted into linear form, and the result is indicated below:

$$\mathbf{GDP_t = b_0 + b_1FRAS_t + b_2PRODt + b_3SOS_t + b_4SECT + et \dots\dots\dots (2)}$$

b_0 captures all other explanatory variables that affect growth but are not captured in the model. 1, 2, 3, and 4 are the parameter coefficients of economic growth with respect to FRAS, PRO, SOS, and SEC, respectively.

3.4. Data collection methods and instruments

The research used two research instruments, which included questionnaires and an interview schedule.

3.4.1 Questionnaires

The questions on the questionnaire were both closed and open-ended; this was done to allow proper expression of the respondent's views on the role of government expenditure on economic development. How many people were given the questionnaires? What was the response rate?

The questions were set on variables such as: the relationship between public expenditure on infrastructure sector and economic growth in South Sudan; the relationship between production sector expenditure by the government and economic growth in South Sudan; the relationship between public expenditure on the social service sector and economic growth in South Sudan; and the relationship between public expenditure on the security sector and economic growth in South Sudan.

4.1.1 Return rate

Table 1: shows the return rate.

Return rate	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Questionnaires Answered	38	86
Questionnaires not returned	6	14
Total Questionnaires distributed	44	100

As represented in the table above, 44 questionnaires were distributed to the Ministry of Finance and Planning, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and the National Revenue Authority; 38 questionnaires were filled out and returned; out of the 44 distributed questionnaires, six were not filled out. The return rate was therefore 86 percent (38). The questionnaires that were not filled was due to lack of knowledge by newly employed staff on the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan

3.4.2 Interview Schedule

An interview was used because it provided an in depth understanding of the problem under instigation. It allowed face-to-face encounters between the researcher and the respondents. How many people were interviewed?

In line with Orodho (2003), during interview, the researcher carried out the interview procedure by using the interview guide that was developed and pretested before going to the field. With the aid of a researcher-made interview schedule, selected staffs were interviewed on various aspects of the impact of government expenditure on economic growth and foreign direct investment.

5.5 Limitations

This study was meant to regroup the ten sectors into four sectors in the following classifications: infrastructure sector, production sector (natural resources, economic functions), social service sector (health, education, public administration, rule of law, social and humanitarian accountability), and security sector. Due to time constraints, the study only considered Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, the National Revenue Authority, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Central Bank of South Sudan (CBSS) which were used assess the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. To

get sufficient information regarding the study secondary data was used to supplement the primary data.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis and discussion of findings on the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan. The study findings were coded and fed into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), IBM Version 21 (2012 edition), and the findings were presented as follows:

4.1 Demographic data for respondents

The demographic information of respondents presented includes the return rate, category of respondents, gender, educational background, and occupation; these are presented as follows:

4.1.1 Education Level

It was sought that the respondent's education level was a significant factor towards assessing the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan; the findings regarding the respondent's education level are represented in Table 4 below.

Table 2: shows the education level.

Education Level		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Secondary	1	2.6	2.6	2.6
	College	4	10.5	10.5	13.2
	University	33	86.8	86.8	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

As represented in table 4 above, the majority of respondents held a university level of education; these were 33 in number and represented 86.8% of the total; these were followed by those that held a college or institute level of education; these are represented by 4 (10.5%), and only 1 (2.6%) held a secondary education level. It was therefore assumed that the majority of respondents were knowledgeable on the subject matter regarding the impact of government expenditure on economic growth.

4.1.2 Work Experience

Work experience was sought to be an important factor in assessing the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan, because the longer the working experience, the more knowledgeable the respondents would be. The findings are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 3: shows work experience.

Work experience		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 Year	3	7.9	7.9	7.9
	1-5 Years	11	28.9	28.9	36.8
	6-10 Years	7	18.4	18.4	55.3
	11-15 Years	10	26.3	26.3	81.6
	16-20 Years	5	13.2	13.2	94.7
	Over 21 Years	2	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

As represented in table 5 above, the majority of respondents had worked in the Ministry of Finance and Planning, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and the National Revenue Authority for 1–5 years; these were represented by 11 (28.9%); these were followed by those that had worked for 11–15 years, represented by 10 (26.3%); those that had worked for 6–10 years, represented by 7, (18.4%); those that had worked for a period of 16–20 years, represented by 5 (13.2%); those that worked for less than a year are represented by 3 (7.9%); and the least were those that had worked for a period of over 21 years.

The study findings show that the majority of respondents had worked for quite a long period of time; this therefore makes them stand out to concisely give a proper trend on the impact of government expenditure on economic development in South Sudan for the period of time that they have worked within the Ministry of Finance and Planning, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and the National Revenue Authority.

4.1.3 Occupation

The findings regarding the occupation of respondents within the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and the National Revenue Authority.

As represented in the table above, the majority of respondents were heads of departments within the Ministry of Finance and Planning, the Central Bank of South Sudan, and the National Revenue Authority; these are represented by 29 (76.3%), followed by accountants represented by 8 (21.1%), and only 1 respondent never disclosed his or her occupation, which is denoted as missing and represented by 2.6%.

4.2 CONTRIBUTIONS OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON REVENUE COLLECTION IN SOUTH SUDAN

Table 4: Government Expenditure and Economic Growth

Findings show that government expenditure is an extremely important factor that promotes national competitiveness and economic growth through government expenditures on technology transfer, new management skills, foreign trade, and corporate productivity. **Table 7** shows that there are 20 respondents (52.6%) that agree, 15 (39.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 1 (2.6%) disagreed, and 1 (2.6%) had no idea whether government expenditure is an extremely important factor that promotes national competitiveness and economic growth through government expenditure on technology transfer, new management skills, foreign trade, and corporate productivity.

Majority respondents that were interviewed indicated that government expenditure on infrastructure improves economic growth.

“Government expenditure on roads such as Juba Bor road, Juba Bahr-el Gazal road will help connect the country to different regions in terms of business and this will boost economic growth”Chuor

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	20	52.6	54.1	54.1
	Strongly Agree	15	39.5	40.5	94.6
	Neutral	1	2.6	2.7	97.3
	Disagree	1	2.6	2.7	100.0
	Total	37	97.4	100 .0	
Missing	System	1	2.6		
Total		38	100.0		

The above findings are similar to a study carried out by Barro (1990), who noted that Government expenditure is one of the important tools which contribute to the economic growth of a nation including South Sudan. Government expenditure includes the allocation provided by the government to carry out various government projects with a desire to enhance the growth of the country’s economy. Most of the government expenditures are funded by the tax revenue collected by the government (Barro, 1990).

Table 5: Government expenditure on tax innovations

The findings in Table 8 indicate that government spending raises national competitiveness and welfare, mainly through increased government expenditure on tax innovations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	17	44.7	47.2	47.2
	Strongly Agree	16	42.1	44.4	91.7
	Neutral	2	5.3	5.6	97.2
	Disagree	1	2.6	2.8	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in table 8 above, the majority of respondents agreed that government expenditure raises national competitiveness and national welfare, mainly through increased government expenditure. On tax innovations, 17 (44.7%) of the respondents agreed, followed by 16 (42.1%) who strongly agreed, and 2 (5.3%) who had no idea

In an interview respondents indicated that government expenditures on public infrastructures such as roads is too low:

“I have noted that for many years government allocate very minial budget to the construction”
Poni

The above findings are similar to a study carried out by Alsadiq, in his study he concluded that Public expenditure policies aimed at increasing public expenditure productivity, though not sufficient, is desirable. Many researchers have examined the effects of aggregate public expenditure on economic growth with mixed results: some support the hypothesis that the share of public spending is negatively associated with economic growth (Alsadiq, 2014).

The above findings are also similar to a study carried out by Gupta *et al.*, (2005), who he found out that reductions in the deficit in Uganda that translate into significant cuts in domestic financing tend to be associated with higher growth rates. In Uganda public financial management reforms, including strict expenditure controls, facilitated a reduction in budget deficits and their monetization, which helped lower inflation.

Table 6: South Sudan tax revenue and Multinational Enterprises (MNEs)

Table 9 below shows that South Sudan loses out on tax revenue when incentives are paid to multinational enterprises (MNEs) or when the problems of transfer pricing (including other tax minimization strategies) are encountered As represented in the table above, the majority of respondents agreed that South Sudan loses out on tax revenue when incentives are paid to multinational enterprises (MNEs) or when the problems of transfer pricing (including other tax

minimization strategies) are encountered, as represented by 13, (34.2%), 7, (18.4%) of the respondents who were neutral or had no idea on the matter, 6 (15.8%) of the respondents who strongly agreed, and 6 (15.8%) of the respondents who strongly disagreed, 4.4% of South Sudan's total assets belong to foreign-owned companies, which indicates that the South Sudan investment regime is one of the most open regimes in the East African region.

From the interviews conducted indicated that South Sudan economy consists of majority foreign companies, Small and Medium Scale Businesses which send money back to their respective countries which has led to decrease in South Sudan's Gross Domestic Product(GDP)

“The market is dominated by foreigners leaving no chance for national to participate in business and hence forth reducing on the county's Gross Domestic Product (GDP)” Cirilo

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	13	34.2	36.1	36.1
	Strongly Agree	6	15.8	16.7	52.8
	Neutral	7	18.4	19.4	72.2
	Disagree	6	15.8	16.7	88.9
	Strongly Disagree	4	10.5	11.1	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

The above findings are similar to a study carried in Australia by Dawkins, the study found out that the Australian Workplace Relations Act 1996 reduced the role of the Industrial Relations Commission in setting wages and conditions primarily by restricting its role to adjudicating on “safety net” wage adjustments. Labor market policies also encouraged the decentralized wage bargaining (Dawkins, 2000).

In 1990, only a third of Australian workers had wages set through enterprise-based or individual contracts. By 2002, this ratio had increased to almost 80 percent (Productivity Commission, 2005). These labor market reforms paid a crucial role in curtailing real wage growth, thus re-establishing external sector competitiveness.

4.5 CONTRIBUTIONS OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN SOUTH SUDAN

This section sought to assess the contributions of government expenditure on infrastructural development in South Sudan. The findings are presented as follows:

Table 7: Government investment

Table below shows the response regarding whether the government has invested in different infrastructural sectors such as the hospitality industry, network, banking, and telecommunication; this has greatly improved the infrastructural status of South Sudan.

Table 10 shows the response on whether the government has invested in different infrastructural sectors such as the hospitality industry, network, banking, and telecommunication, which has greatly improved the infrastructural status of South Sudan.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	19	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Strongly Agree	14	36.8	36.8	86.8
	Neutral	2	5.3	5.3	92.1
	Disagree	1	2.6	2.6	94.7
	Strongly Disagree	2	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

As represented in Table 10 above, the majority of respondents (19, or 50%) agreed that the government has invested in different infrastructural sectors such as the hospitality industry, network, banking, and telecommunication; this has greatly improved the infrastructural status of South Sudan. 14 (36.8%) strongly agreed, 2 (5.3%) were neutral, 2 (5.3%) strongly disagreed, and 1 (2.6%) declined to respond.

(Antwi, 2013) carried out a study on the impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth of Pakistan for the period 1981 to 2010. They used six variables where GDP is specified as dependent variable while FDI, Total debt Service, Gross Domestic Savings, Inflation, as independent variables. The findings indicated a negative and significant relationship between FDI and dependent variable GDP. Also Debt, Inflation and Trade exhibited negative relationship with GDP. In conclusion, they stated that Domestic Investment will be more beneficial and that dependency on FDI should be limited. They recommended that the Government should encourage domestic savings and investment. They suggest further studies to incorporate variables relating to technology transfer and Human Capital.

From the interviews conducted the following responses were recorded.

“Infrastructural development such roads for example Juba Nimule road, Juba Bor road, Juba Bahar El Gazal road have connected the capital to other regions which has eased business” Emmanuel

“South Sudan telecommunication commission has done its best to improve communication media such as the internet fibre connected to South Sudan right from East Africa” Angelina.

Table 8: Physical infrastructure and economic development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	6	15.8	16.2	16.2
	Strongly Agree	22	57.9	59.5	75.7
	Neutral	4	10.5	10.8	86.5
	Disagree	4	10.5	10.8	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	1	2.6	2.7	100.0
	Total	37	97.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	2.6		
Total		38	100.0		

Majority respondents: 22 (57.9%) strongly agreed, 6 (15.8%) agreed, 4 (10.5%) were neutral, 4 (10.5%) disagreed, and 1 (2.6%) declined to respond. The above studies are similar to study by (Bunescu, 2014) carried out a study on economic and non-economic factors that affect tax revenues in 27 EU countries over 1995–2011. Using correlation analysis, they revealed that FDI inflows had a weak positive effect on tax revenues. On the other side, Tabasam (2014) investigated the interaction between tax revenues and foreign capital inflows (FCIs) in Pakistan during 1975–2012. Using time series analysis, he concluded that FDI inflows hurt tax revenues. Besides, Aslam (2015) examined the long-run relationship between FDI inflows and tax revenues in Sri Lanka over 1990–2013 and discovered that FDI inflows made a significant positive contribution to tax revenues.

Table 9: Role played by government of South Sudan in infrastructural development

The study sought to assess whether foreign governments in South Sudan have taken up different contracts such as oil exploration, road construction, and networking, and whether this has greatly contributed to the development of infrastructural infrastructure in the country. The findings are presented in Table 13 below.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	12	31.6	33.3	33.3
	Strongly Agree	13	34.2	36.1	69.4
	Neutral	10	26.3	27.8	97.2
	Strongly Disagree	1	2.6	2.8	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Majority of the respondents 13 (34.2%) strongly agreed that the government of South Sudan has taken up different contracts such as oil exploration, road construction, and networking, and this has greatly contributed to the development of the infrastructural development in South Sudan. 12 (31.6%) agreed, 10 (26.3%) had no idea, and lastly, only 1 (2.6%) strongly disagreed.

A study by (Okey, 2013) also studied the effect of FDI inflows on tax revenue mobilization in West Africa over 1989–2009. Using a panel regression, he concluded that FDI inflows positively impact tax revenues. However, the findings may not be generalized to other countries of South Saharan Africa because the investigation is limited to only French-speaking members of ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States), and these countries have political and economic characteristics different from those of English speaking countries in the West African Region.

Table 10: Impact of quality of physical infrastructure

The study sought to assess the respondent’s views on whether good physical infrastructure would improve the investment climate for government expenditures as the cost of total investment by foreign investors could be subsidized, therefore increasing the rate of return. The findings that were obtained are presented in the table below.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	9	23.7	24.3	24.3
	Strongly Agree	13	34.2	35.1	59.5
	Neutral	8	21.1	21.6	81.1
	Disagree	4	10.5	10.8	91.9
	Strongly Disagree	3	7.9	8.1	100.0
	Total	37	97.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	2.6		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in Table 13 above, the majority of respondents (13, 34%) strongly agreed that with good quality physical infrastructure, the investment climate for government expenditure would improve as the cost of total investment by foreign investors can be subsidized, therefore increasing the rate of return. 9 (23.7%) agreed, 8 (21.1%) were neutral, 4 (10.5%) disagreed, and 3 (7.9%) strongly disagreed.

(Dunning, 1993) investigated the FDI effect through the determinants of tax revenues, he indicated that welfare effects of FDI in the host country depend on the bargaining power of the host country with foreign investors, including either by offering the tax rebates on energy or labor costs to attract foreign investment or by imposing the tax. He further claimed that FDI could create employment, transfer technology through training local labor, and improve management skills; the government should lose some tax revenue to attract foreign investment inflow.

4.6 CHALLENGES FACING GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON INFRASTRUCTURE IN SOUTH SUDAN

This section sought to assess the challenges facing government expenditure on infrastructure in South Sudan. The findings that were obtained are presented as follows:

Table 11: Insecurity

Different respondents were asked to indicate whether the high rate of insecurity in South Sudan discourages government expenditure; the findings are presented in Table 15 below.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	9	23.7	24.3	24.3
	Strongly Agree	22	57.9	59.5	83.8
	Neutral	1	2.6	2.7	86.5
	Disagree	2	5.3	5.4	91.9
	Strongly Disagree	3	7.9	8.1	100.0
	Total	37	97.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	2.6		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in Table 14 above, the majority of respondents (22, or 57.9%) indicated that the high rate of insecurity in South Sudan discourages government expenditure. 9 (23.7%) agreed, 3 (7.9%) strongly disagreed, 2 (5.3%) disagreed, 1 (1.26%) had no idea, and 1 (2.6%) declined to

answer. In a study carried out by Morduch since developing countries are the most poverty stricken, the World Bank has tried to establish a universal benchmark for the poverty line. The poverty line establishes the income or spending level that individuals and households require in order to purchase essential services such as food, shelter, water, education and health (Morduch 2005). The poverty is the minimum household expenditure or income required to consume basic goods and services (World Bank Institute 2005). Individuals and households below the poverty line are considered poor

Table 12: Policies promoting infrastructural development in South Sudan

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	15	39.5	41.7	41.7
	Strongly Agree	5	13.2	13.9	55.6
	Neutral	9	23.7	25.0	80.6
	Disagree	7	18.4	19.4	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Figure 15 above shows that the majority of respondents, 15 (39.5%), agreed that low-rate policies aimed at promoting infrastructural development in South Sudan are one of the challenges facing the government. Nine (23.7%) were neutral, seven (18.4%) disagreed, five (13.2%) strongly agreed, and two (5.3%) declined to answer probably because they were newly appointed in those positions and therefore had limited information.

According to UNCTAD (2009a) infrastructural investments are either legally binding or non-legally binding. The Memorandum of Understanding is a non-legally binding agreement intended to formalize the willingness of the contracting parties to collaborate in the specific areas agreed upon; these involve low-rate policies aimed at promoting infrastructural development in South Sudan. There are three legally binding investment agreements: BITs, comprehensive Free Trade Areas (FTAs) and Double Taxation Avoidance Agreement. BITs provide provisions for investment promotion and protection. Comprehensive FTAs are aimed at promoting investments among the contracting parties.

From the interviews conducted the following responses were noted.

“South Sudan security forces have caused more fear among investors due to exorbitant taxes levies on both investors and business men at the border and during transit of goods, this is a sign

of poor implementation of policies put in place to safeguard investors and business men within the country” Lodule

Table 13: Delay in Government expenditure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	7	18.4	19.4	19.4
	Strongly Agree	16	42.1	44.4	63.9
	Neutral	7	18.4	19.4	83.3
	Disagree	2	5.3	5.6	88.9
	Strongly Disagree	4	10.5	11.1	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Table 16 indicates that 16 (42.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed that one of the challenges facing foreign governments is government expenditure delays due to government bureaucracy and local political demands; 7 (18.4%) agreed, 7 (18.4%) were neutral, 4 (10.5%) disagreed, and 2 (5.3%) declined to answer.

From the interviews conducted the following response was conducted.

“Delays in government expenditure are due to government bureaucracy and local political demands that include giving of bribe to those involved in processing of business related registration, clearance among others” Valentino

Table 14: Increased government expenditure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	7	18.4	19.4	19.4
	Strongly Agree	19	50.0	52.8	72.2
	Neutral	6	15.8	16.7	88.9
	Disagree	2	5.3	5.6	94.4
	Strongly Disagree	2	5.3	5.6	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Table 17 above shows that 19 (50%) of the respondents strongly agreed that one of the challenges facing foreign investors is increased government expenditure, which leads to over-reliance, which makes a country too dependent on it and may turn into a risk.

Table 15: Status of Domestic firms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	11	28.9	32.4	32.4
	Strongly Agree	2	5.3	35.3	67.6
	Neutral	5	13.2	14.7	82.4
	Disagree	12	31.6	5.9	88.2
	Strongly Disagree	4	10.5	11.8	100.0
	Total	34	89.5	100.0	
Missing	System	4	10.5		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in table 18 above, the majority of respondents disagreed that domestic firms may suffer if they are relatively uncompetitive; this is not a challenge facing foreign direct investors. Eleven (28.9%) agreed, five (13.2%) were neutral, and four (10.5%) strongly agreed.

The above findings are similar to a study carried out by (Daniel W. , 2013) he found that performance and delivery of good services and products by any SME dependent on the external pressure that arise as a result of competition.

From the interviews conducted, *“South Sudan economy is a free economy comprising of owners of SMEs controlling the price of goods, this has forces, it is also characterized by stiff competition” Cirilo Chol*

4.7 SOLUTIONS TO THE CHALLENGES FACING GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE IN SOUTH SUDAN

This section presents the solutions to the challenges facing government expenditure in South Sudan; the findings are presented in table

Table 16: Need for the government of South Sudan to prioritize security

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	9	23.7	24.3	24.3
	Strongly Agree	26	68.4	70.3	94.6
	Neutral	1	2.6	2.7	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	1	2.6	2.7	100.0
	Total	37	97.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	2.6		
Total		38	100.0		

According to table 19, the majority of respondents strongly agreed that there is a need for the government of South Sudan to prioritize security arrangements to promote Government Expenditure, 9 (23.7%) agreed, 1 (2.6%) strongly disagreed, 1 (2.6%) were neutral, and 1 (2.6%) declined to answer.

Table 17: Develop policies aimed at promoting government expenditure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	18	47.4	50.0	50.0
	Strongly Agree	16	42.1	44.4	94.4
	Neutral	1	2.6	2.8	97.2
	Disagree	1	2.6	2.8	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Majority respondents 18 (47.4%) agreed that there is a need to come up with policies aimed at promoting government expenditure in South Sudan, 16 (42.1%) strongly agreed, 1 (2.6%) was neutral, and 1 (2.6%) of the respondents declined to answer.

Table 18: The government should highly invest in local production.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	6	15.8	18.8	18.8
	Strongly Agree	24	63.2	75.0	93.8
	Neutral	2	5.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	32	84.2	100.0	
Missing	System	6	15.8		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in table 21 above, the majority of respondents, 24 (63.2%), strongly agreed that the government should highly invest in local production, 6 (15.8%) were neutral, and 6 (15.8%) declined to answer.

Table 19: Give incentives to local investors to improve their competitive advantage.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	13	34.2	37.1	37.1
	Strongly Agree	15	39.5	42.9	80.0
	Neutral	2	5.3	5.7	85.7
	Disagree	3	7.9	8.6	94.3
	Strongly Disagree	2	5.3	5.7	100.0
	Total	35	92.1	100.0	
Missing	System	3	7.9		
Total		38	100.0		

Table 22 above shows that the majority of respondents (15, 39.5%) strongly agreed that the government of South Sudan should give incentives to local investors to improve their competitive advantage. 13 (34.2%) agreed, 3 (7.9%) disagreed, 2 (5.3%) strongly disagreed, and 3 (7.9%) declined to answer.

Table 20: Increase local production, reducing importation, and increasing exportation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	7	18.4	20.0	20.0
	Strongly Agree	25	65.8	71.4	91.4
	Neutral	3	7.9	8.6	100.0
	Total	35	92.1	100.0	
Missing	System	3	7.9		
Total		38	100.0		

As represented in table 23 above, the majority of respondents, 25 (65.8%), strongly agreed that one of the solutions to the challenges facing foreign governments is that South Sudan should increase its market size by increasing local production, reducing importation, and increasing exportation; 7 (18.4%) agreed, 3 (7.9%) were neutral, and 3 (7.9%) declined to answer.

Table 21: Prioritize in infrastructure investment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	13	34.2	37.1	37.1
	Strongly Agree	19	50.0	54.3	91.4
	Neutral	1	2.6	2.9	94.3
	Strongly Disagree	2	5.3	5.7	100.0
	Total	35	92.1	100.0	
Missing	System	3	7.9		
Total		38	100.0		

Table A above shows that the majority of respondents (19, or 50%) strongly agreed that one of the solutions to challenges facing foreign governments is that the South Sudan government should prioritize investing in infrastructure quality, 13 (34.2%) agreed, 2 (7.9%) strongly disagreed, and 3 (7.9%) declined to answer.

Table 22: Participate in regional trade platforms such as the Free Trade Area

The study sought to assess if South Sudan's active participation in regional trade platforms such as the Free Trade Area could be a solution to the challenges facing foreign governments in South Sudan. Different respondents were required to indicate whether they agreed or disagreed; the findings are presented in Table 25 below.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	12	31.6	33.3	33.3
	Strongly Agree	12	31.6	33.3	66.7
	Neutral	4	10.5	11.1	77.8
	Disagree	7	18.4	19.4	97.2
	Strongly Disagree	1	2.6	2.8	100.0
	Total	36	94.7	100.0	
Missing	System	2	5.3		
Total		38	100.0		

Table 25 above shows that the majority of respondents strongly agreed and others agreed, represented by 12 (31.6%) respectively, that South Sudan should actively participate in regional trade platforms such as the Free Trade Area. Seven (18.4%) of the respondents disagreed, and one (2.6%) strongly disagreed.

Table 23: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The analysis of variance between government expenditure on infrastructure and economic growth was carried out using Friedman's Test in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS); the findings are presented in Table 26 below.

ANOVA with Friedman's Test						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Friedman's Chi-Square	Sig
Between Variables		16.629	33	.504		
Within Variables	Between Items	.180 ^a	1	.180	.612	.434
	Residual	9.820	33	.298		
	Total	10.000	34	.294		
Total		26.629	67	.397		
Grand Mean = 2.0956						
a. Kendall's coefficient of concordance W = .007.						

The table shows the significant results as the value of 0.434 is greater than Kendall's coefficient of 0.007. It means that different government expenditures have different impacts on economic growth, and therefore government expenditure has a positive impact on economic growth for all kinds of expenditures.

The above findings are similar to a study by (Ibrahim, 2014), the ANOVA findings of the processed data at 5% level of significance showed that F calculated value is 16.384 while F critical is 4.35 at d.f 3 and 7. Therefore, F calculated is greater than F critical which shows that the overall regression model was a significant predictor of the relationship between the variables of the study. The p value $0.002 < 0.05$ further supports the argument of significance. This showed that as broad money reduces, economic growth increases. In reality however, it is expected that an increase in money supply results into economic growth especially during deflationary times. It is only during times of extreme inflation (hyperinflation or stagflation) where a decrease in money supply would result in economic growth which shall make sense in view of this finding.

Table 24: Correlation Analysis

This table shows Spearman's rank-correlation analysis of government expenditures and the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. The relationship among these variables is given below.

Correlations								
			Economic Growth	Relationship	Government expenditure			
Spearman's rho	Economic Growth	Correlation Coefficient			1.000	.828	.773	
		Sig. (2-tailed)			.	.000	.000	
		N			34	34	34	
		Bootstrap ^a	Bias			.000	-.014	-.009
			Std. Error			.000	.065	.081
			95% Confidence Interval	Lower		1.000	.650	.594
	Upper			1.000	.919	.894		
	Relationship	Correlation Coefficient			.828	1.000	.344	
		Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.	.046	
		N			34	34	34	
		Bootstrap ^a	Bias			-.014	.000	-.012
			Std. Error			.065	.000	.146
			95% Confidence Interval	Lower		.650	1.000	.035
	Upper			.919	1.000	.604		
	Government expenditure	Correlation Coefficient			.773	.344	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.046	.	
		N			34	34	34	
		Bootstrap ^a	Bias			-.009	-.012	.000
Std. Error			.081	.146	.000			
95% Confidence Interval			Lower		.594	.035	1.000	
	Upper		.894	.604	1.000			

a. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 1000 bootstrap samples

b. *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The findings show that the composition of public outlays is positively correlated with economic growth of who decisively recognized a correlation between public expenditure and economic growth.

Economic growth

The table shows a negative relationship (-.009) between economic growth and government expenditure. It means that the government has done less in terms of infrastructural development to boost economic growth.

Relationship between economic growth and government expenditure

The table shows a positive relationship (sig value = 0.46) between government expenditure on infrastructure and economic development, which is greater than the correlation coefficient of

0.05. It means that if there is an increase in government expenditure on infrastructure, it will also increase economic growth. So there is a direct relationship between these variables.

4.10 Interpretation of Findings and Discussions

From correlation results, broad money had a Pearson correlation of -0.159 with p value was 0.002. The value of r is negative showing an inverse relationship between broad money and economic growth. This shows that as broad money reduces, economic growth increases. In reality however, it is expected that an increase in money supply results into economic growth especially during deflationary times. It is only during times of extreme inflation (hyperinflation or stagflation) where a decrease in money supply would result in economic growth which shall make sense in view of this finding. According to (Onwumere, Ibe, Ozoh, & Mounanu, 2012) broad money velocity and market liquidity promoted economic growth.

The findings of correlation analysis further indicated that private sector credit had a Pearson correlation r of 0.893 with p value 0.000. The value of r is positive and significant. It is significant because the p value is less than 0.05. It is positive showing that as private sector credit increases, economic growth is also achieved in the country. This is practically true since the money issued to private developers are used for creation of jobs, production of goods and services that increase consumption and therefore economic growth. This finding therefore indicates that financial intermediaries have played a significant role in the economic growth of the country. This finding contradicts with (Nzotta & Okereke, 2009) who established financial system had not played its intermediation role effectively especially in the area of credit allocation and in the monetization of the economy.

Correlation analysis results further indicated that market capitalization to GDP had a Pearson correlation of 0.846 with p 0.001 which is less than 0.05. The value of r is strong and positive. This shows that as market capitalization increase, economic growth is also enhanced. Market capitalization aggregates the total value of all listed firms at NSE over a given period of time. An increase in market capitalization shows that more shares have been moved on the security exchange market for example the Nairobi Security Exchange NSE. Securities traded on an exchange market include common stock commonly called ordinary shares or equities, fixed income securities like corporate bonds and treasury bonds. This finding is in line with Alrabadi and (Nzotta & Okereke, 2009) who established that a statistically significant long run equilibrium relationship existed between financial deepening and economic growth regardless

of the proxy used for financial deepening.

From the findings of regression analysis, the p value for private sector credit was less than 0.05. This shows that private sector credit significantly contributes towards economic growth of the country as a whole. In other words, it is a significant factor with far reaching effect on economic growth of the country as a whole. This finding is in line with (Nzotta & Okereke, 2009) who indicated that capital market deepening positively affected GDP growth which lends support to the finance growth nexus.

Regression results further indicated that market capitalization had p value less than 0.05 and therefore significant indicator of economic growth. The effect of market capitalization can best be illustrated by the market intermediation theory where NSE and other lending institutions play significant role in growth of the economy. The Financial Intermediation Theory is concerned with the role played by financial intermediaries in an economy. Financial sector plays the main role of financial intermediation in any economy by electing surplus resources from households and redirecting the same resources to deficient households with investment ideas but limited in resources

On a comparative level, of the inferential statistics, correlation analysis established all the independent variables (money supply, private sector credit and market capitalization) while regression analysis only indicated two independent variables (money supply and private sector credit) to have significant influence on economic growth. The general observation from these two inferential statistics therefore is that financial deepening significantly affects economic growth in Kenya. Bakang sought to determine how liquidity, credit to private sector, assets owned by banks expressed as a ratio to all banks and central bank assets put together, commercial bank deposits as a ratio to GDP affected economic growth as measured by real GDP. The findings indicated that all the four variables assessed produced positive and statistically significant effect on GDP (Nzotta & Okereke, 2009).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the summary, conclusion, and recommendations of the study regarding the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in South Sudan.

5.1 Summary

5.1.1 The relationship between public expenditure and economic growth in South Sudan

The study's findings indicated that the following are relationships between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth in South Sudan:

Government expenditure is an extremely important factor that promotes national competitiveness and economic growth through technology transfer, new management skills, foreign trade, and corporate productivity.

Government expenditure raises national competitiveness and welfare, mainly through increased government expenditure on tax innovations.

South Sudan loses out on tax revenue when incentives are paid to multinational enterprises (MNEs) or when the problems of transfer pricing (including other tax minimization strategies) are countered.

South Sudan's total assets belong to foreign-owned companies, which indicates that the South Sudan investment regime is one of the most open regimes in the East African region.

Government expenditures and investors have provided direct jobs to South Sudanese.

The effect of government expenditure on tax revenue is intended to contribute to the development of relevant policies. The national government of South Sudan should continue its government expenditure promotion policies.

The impact of government expenditure on tax revenue depends on competition and technology spillovers from multinational companies (MNCs); this stimulates productivity and, hence, increases revenues collected and the Gross Domestic Product of South Sudan.

Government expenditure inflows raise corporate tax payments in South Sudan; this impact is found among the greatest in high-tech companies in the country.

Tax revenue is affected by several national financial and economic factors such as cash surplus deficit and government expenditure net inflow, which are the key factors that significantly affect tax revenue in South Sudan.

5.1.2 Contributions of government expenditure on infrastructural development

The study findings indicate that the following are contributions of government expenditure on infrastructural development:

With a good quality of physical infrastructure, the investment climate for government expenditures would improve as the cost of total investment by foreign investors could be subsidized, therefore increasing the rate of return.

Generally, a country with good physical infrastructure, such as highways, ports, bridges, and communications, is likely to attract more government expenditure.

Foreign direct investors have invested in different infrastructural sectors such as the hospitality industry, network, banking, and telecommunication, which has greatly improved the infrastructural status of South Sudan.

Through foreign direct investors in South Sudan, these have taken up different contracts such as oil exploration, road construction, and networking, and this has greatly contributed to the development of the infrastructural development in South Sudan.

5.1.3 Challenges facing government expenditures in South Sudan

The study findings indicate the following as solutions to the challenges affecting government expenditure in South Sudan:

There is a high rate of insecurity in South Sudan, which discourages government expenditure.

Low-rate policies aimed at promoting foreign direct investment in South Sudan

Government expenditure delays due to government bureaucracy and local political demands

Increased government expenditure brings over-reliance, which makes a country too dependent on it and may turn into a risk.

Domestic firms may suffer if they are relatively uncompetitive.

South Sudan has a very small market, which discourages government expenditure.

South Sudan has poor infrastructure quality, which discourages government expenditure.

South Sudan does not actively participate in free trade zones in the region.

5.1.4 Solutions to the challenges affecting government expenditure in South Sudan

The study found the following to be solutions to the challenges affecting government expenditure in South Sudan:

There is a need for the government of South Sudan to prioritize security arrangements to promote government expenditure.

There is a need to come up with policies aimed at promoting government expenditure in South Sudan.

The government should heavily invest in local production.

The government of South Sudan should give incentives to local investors to improve their competitive advantage.

South Sudan should increase its market size by increasing local production, reducing importation, and increasing exportation.

South Sudan's government should prioritize high-quality infrastructure investment.

South Sudan should actively participate in regional trade platforms such as the Free Trade Area.

5.1.5 Correlation Analysis

According to the findings of the study, it is clear that public spending on the infrastructure sector had a positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth. This implies that spending on gross fixed capital formation, like roads, railways, dams, schools, and hospitals, would accelerate the badly needed economic growth for the young country. Since the P value is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth.

5.2 Conclusion

The infrastructure sector has a positive and statistically significant relationship with growth in the gross domestic product (GDP). This implies that spending on gross fixed capital formation, like roads, railways, dams, schools, and hospitals, would accelerate the needed economic growth for the young country.

This study used panel data and estimated the regression of a random effects model; this means analysis on the co-integration between variables and investigation of the long-run and short-run relationships between the variables carried out in another study when adequate expenditure data were available for research.

The findings showed that public expenditure on infrastructure, productive, and security sectors is significant and positive determinant of economic growth, while public expenditure on the social services sector impacts economic growth negatively.

The results of this project report emphasize that the composition of public expenditure is important for economic growth; however, the study has not exhausted all the components of public expenditure, including those of the states and counties in South Sudan. Given the above, this research recommends the following:

5.3 Recommendations

Several policy recommendations have been drawn from the research findings, these are summarized below;

The government should increase its investment in areas that are beneficial to the private sector and eschew from those that compete with or crowd it out. It should Increase its expenditure on those items that enter private production functions as productive public inputs that enhances economic growth. Such productive government investment expenditure includes expenditure on buildings, plant, machinery and equipment all of which generate positive externalities that raise private investment and thus economic growth.

The government should allocate more resources to areas of physical infrastructural development more that what was budgeted for in previous years such as that of the 2019/2020 113,377m was Planned, the Actual expenditure was 114,620m, the figure Over spent amounted to 1243m

in order to stimulate economic growth as envisaged in it future vision. This is because additional expenditure on physical infrastructure in such areas as roads, railways, ports, communication, water and electricity contribute significantly to the economic growth by increasing the marginal productivity of inputs in the private and public sectors. Furthermore, high government expenditure on transportation and communication and energy create an enabling environment for business to thrive through reduced cost of production.

The government should increase it its expenditure allocation to the education and human capital development. This could be done through provision of proper education facilities such as schools colleges and universities, training and employing more teachers, ensuring access to education to all citizens, reduction of the cost burden to the parents/guardian and expanding education to the marginalized groups. This is because quality education creates positive externalities and increases the productive capacity that helps to raise the steady state rate of economic growth.

The government should allocate more funds for the development of the health care sector. In 2019/2020 the planned budget was 2,241m and the **actual expenditure was 2,246m**. This should

be achieved through investment in proper capital equipment's, health facilities and provision of quality medical supplies.

The government should also consider human capital investment through training of the human resources relevant to this sector such as doctors and nurses. This is because, when there was an increase in expenditure allocation to the health care sector, the level of economic growth increased since a health nation is a wealth nation.

The government should streamline its allocation to the debt servicing. This is because public debt servicing reduces the resources that could otherwise have been allocated to more productive sectors of the economy.

Furthermore, public debt servicing crowd out private investment which affect economic growth adversely. The reduction in public debt can be achieved by reducing government borrowing and ensuring that borrowed loans are concessional in nature. This means that since the government would have a long repayment period at a lower interest rate, the burden on public debt would be lesser.

The allocation to economic affairs should be increased by the government. This would be achieved by ensuring that the sectors that are productive in nature under this allocation are accorded the right attention while those that are non-productive in nature are rationalized. This is because economic affairs provide a direct provision of productive activities through its expenditure in areas of Advances in Economics and Business 5(12): 635-662, 2017 659 maintenance and operations, agriculture, manufacturing, trade, mining, fisheries, forestry, tourism and construction.

The government should streamline its expenditure allocation to the general administration and services and also increase its efficiency in service delivery. This would go a long way in saving funds that could be used in other priority sectors. This implies that the government should have sustainable policies for development to avoid crowding out the private investors who play a vital role to the growth and development of the economy. The efficiency in government sector could also lead to improved efficiency in the markets for goods and services, factor market and financial asset markets that help to mobilize resources for private investment.

The government should increase its expenditure allocation to defense and public order and national security. This is because, when the allocation to these sectors is increased, there is a positive change in economic growth. These sectors help to improve security within the economy

thereby increasing economic activities in areas of tourism and private investment. In addition, the sectors help to increase competition in the economy due to increased protection and enforcement of government legal structure. Effort should be made by the government to reduce its consumption. This is because increased government consumption crowds out private investments and reduces the disposable income of the people which result to reduced household consumption in the economy.

The government should restructure government expenditure through budget rationalization in order to achieve an effective public sector. It is important for policy makers to pay attention not just to the levels of government expenditure, but also to its composition. Besides, prioritization of government expenditure should be judged not only by virtue of its economic returns, but also on the technical, administrative and financial feasibility front

Proper measure of cost and benefits of various government expenditures is essential in this respect. A clear set of specified criteria for deciding the allocations of resources should be followed to avoid arbitrary allocation and rent seeking by promoting transparency and accountability. This requires long-term programs of budget rationalization focusing on elimination of wasteful and unproductive expenditure thus improving equity through distributional impacts and maximizing economic growth by ensuring that fiscal operations are conducted in the least cost manner.

In order to reduce the rate of growth of expenditure on salaries and allowances, the government should streamline its civil service to the minimum by freezing recruitments and increasing wage in line with the economic growth. The government should also adopt the advanced technologies in its service delivery in order to cut down the size of civil service. This is because reduced civil service helps in the diversion of resources from unproductive expenditure on wages and salaries, to a more productive expenditure in form of infrastructure and education.

The government should reduce its size to an optimal one by adopting a policy on privatization and expenditure downsizing and outsourcing to cut its expenditure and in turn ease public debt. This is because running a large public debt for a long-period of time could have an adverse effect on the economic growth since borrowing might crowd out private sector investment.

Donors and development partners should partner with government in creating a platform for investment and development and support the initiatives spearheaded by the government.

Regional integration should be explored to ensure that gains that could be obtained regionally such as trade and industrialization are maximized.

The private sector should partner with government in provision of certain services through Public-Private Partnership (PPP). This could be achieved through joint efforts in provision of services such as infrastructure, energy, health and education.

Individuals on the other hand should be responsible citizens, hardworking and business minded by engaging in entrepreneurial ventures. This should be done by people in all walks of life to ensure a cohesive and prosperous nation

5.4 Areas for Further Research

It is also important to mention that the government may have other objectives other than promoting economic growth for example, inducing some redistribution of income, which are not visible in national accounts figures, and that certainly explains a partially the government expenditure behavior on economic growth.

In future work, it would be important to extend the sample size to test for the robustness of the results. In view of political challenges such as the demographic burden and climatic change, it becomes increasingly important to explore further what portfolio of government outlays is optimal in economic growth and welfare terms.

Future research should be devoted to the complex transmission channel leading from government expenditure to economic growth. Finally, although the focus of this study is solely on measuring the impact of government expenditure on economic growth, an important issue to address in future research is what determines government decision to allocate expenditure among various components. In particular, the role of demographic factors and the nature of the political process

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APPENDICES

Appendix one: Questionnaire

UNIVERSITY OF JUBA
SCHOOL OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC STUDIES
DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMICS
QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondent,

I am **Akau Maker Nyuon Yool**, a student at the University of Juba **School of Social and Economic Studies, Department of Economics**, pursuing a master's degree in economics. I am carrying out a research project on "**The Impact of Government Expenditure on Economic Growth in South Sudan**".

(Please answer all questions honestly and exhaustively by ticking in the appropriate box that closely matches your view and/or writing in the spaces provided where necessary.)

Definition of Key Concepts in this Questionnaire

Government expenditure: This includes all government consumption, investment, and transfer payments.

Economic growth is an increase in the quantity and quality of the economic goods and services that a society produces and consumes.

Foreign direct investment, or FDI, is one of the most crucial channels of direct investment between countries.

AKAU MAKER NYUON YOOL

REG. No: 2020 -MSc-041

Contact: +211 (0)92 818 7015, Email; akaumaker2021@gmail.com

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. What is your gender?

- a) Male
- b) Female

2. Educational level

- a) Primary
- b) Secondary
- c) College
- d) University

3. Work experience

- a) Less than 1 year
- b) 1 -5 years
- c) 6-10 years
- d) 11- 15 years
- e) 16-20 years
- f) Over 21 years

4. Occupation

- a) Civil Servant
- b) Foreign Direct Investor
- c) Others, please mention.....

Section B: The Relationship between Public Expenditure on the Infrastructure Sector and Economic Growth in South Sudan

1. Please indicate by ticking () how you agree on the following relationships between public expenditure on the infrastructure sector and economic growth in South

Sudan. Use the Like scale of agree (A), strongly agree (SA), neutral (N), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) to rate your option.

No	Contributions of Government expenditure on Revenue Collection in South Sudan	A	SA	N	D	SD
1	Government Expenditure is an extremely important factor that promotes national competitiveness and economic growth through Government Expenditure on technology transfer, new management skills, foreign trade, corporate productivity					
2	Government Expenditure raises national competitiveness and national welfare, mainly through increased Government Expenditure on tax innovations					
3	South Sudan loses out on tax revenue when incentives are paid to multinational enterprises (MNEs) or when the problems of transfer pricing (including other tax minimization strategies) are encountered					
4	South Sudan total assets belong to foreign-owned companies, which indicate that the South Sudan investment regime is one of the most open regimes in the East African region. Government Expenditure Investors have provided direct jobs to South Sudanese					
5	The effect of Government Expenditure on tax revenue is intended to contribute to the development of the relevant policies. The national of South Sudan should continue its Government Expenditure promotion policies.					
6	The impact of Government Expenditure on tax revenue depends on competition and technology spillovers from multinational companies (MNCs); this stimulate productivity and hence forth increase revenues collected and Gross Domestic Product of South Sudan.					
7	Government Expenditure inflows raise corporate tax payments in South Sudan; this impact is found among the greatest in					

	high-tech companies in South Sudan.					
8	Tax revenue is affected by several national financial and economic factors such as cash surplus deficit, and Government Expenditure net inflow which are the key factor that significantly affects tax revenue in South Sudan					

2. **For any other contributions to government expenditure in South Sudan, please mention**

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.....

Section D: Contributions of Government Expenditures on Infrastructure Development

Please indicate by ticking () how you agree on the following contributions of foreign direct investment to infrastructural development in South Sudan. Use the Like scale of agree (A), strongly agree (SA), neutral (N), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) to rate your option.

No	Contributions of Government Expenditure on infrastructural development in South Sudan	A	SA	N	D	SD
1	With a good quality of physical infrastructure the investment climate for Government Expenditure would improve as the cost of total investment by foreign investor can be subsidized, therefore increase the rate of return.					
2	Generally, a country with good physical infrastructures such as highways, ports, bridges, communications, are likely to attract more Government Expenditure					
3	Foreign Direct Investors have Invested in different					

	infrastructural sectors such as hospitality industry, network, banking, telecommunication, this has greatly improved the infrastructural status of South Sudan					
4	Through Foreign Direct Investors in South Sudan, these have taken up different contracts such as oil exploration, road construction, networking and this has greatly contributed to development of the infrastructural development in South Sudan					
5	The contribution of Foreign Direct Investors verses local investors is overweight in favor of Foreign Direct Investors, therefore Foreign Direct Investors have greatly contributed to infrastructural development, an example are manufacturing industries such water bottling companies owned majorly by Ethiopians					

1. For any other contributions of foreign direct investment to infrastructural development in South Sudan, please mention

.....
.....

SECTION E: CHALLENGES FACING GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURES IN SOUTH SUDAN

2. Please indicate by ticking () how you agree with the following statement regarding the challenges facing government expenditure in South Sudan. Use the Like scale of agree (A), strongly agree (SA), neutral (N), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) to rate your option.

No	Challenges facing Foreign Direct Investors in South Sudan	A	SA	N	D	SD
1	There is high rate insecurity in South Sudan, this discourages Government Expenditure					
2	Low rate policies aimed at promoting Foreign Direct Investment in South Sudan					

3	Government Expenditure delays due to government bureaucracy and local political demands					
4	Increased Government Expenditure brings over-reliance which makes a country too dependent on it and it may turn into a risk					
5	Domestic firms may suffer if they are relatively uncompetitive					
6	South Sudan has a very low market size, this discourages Government Expenditure					
7	South Sudan has poor infrastructure quality, this discourages Government Expenditure					
	South Sudan does not actively participate in free trade zones in the region					

3. **For any other challenges facing government expenditure in South Sudan, please mention**

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.....

SECTION F: SOLUTIONS TO THE CHALLENGES AFFECTING GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE IN SOUTH SUDAN

1. Please indicate by ticking () how you agree with the following statement regarding solutions to the challenges facing government expenditure in South Sudan. Use the Like scale of agree (A), strongly agree (SA), neutral (N), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) to rate your option.

No	Solutions to the challenges facing Foreign Direct Investors in South Sudan	A	SA	N	D	SD
1	There is need for government of South Sudan to prioritize on security arrangements to promote Government Expenditure					
2	There is need to come up with policies aimed at promoting					

	Government Expenditure in South Sudan					
4	Government should highly invest in local production					
5	Government of South Sudan should give incentives to local investors to improve their competitive advantage					
6	South Sudan should increase on its market size by increasing local production and reduce importation and increase exportation					
7	South Sudan government should prioritize in investing on infrastructure quality					
	South Sudan should actively participate in regional trade platforms such Free Trade Area					

2. **For any other solutions to the challenges of government expenditure in South Sudan, please mention**

.....

END

Thank you for participating in this research exercise.

Appendix Two: Interview Guide

UNIVERSITY OF JUBA
SCHOOL OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC STUDIES
DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMICS

1. What are the contributions of Foreign Direct Investment on revenue collection in South Sudan?
2. What is the level of infrastructural development done by foreign investors in South Sudan?
3. What are the challenges affecting foreign investors in South Sudan?
4. What are the solutions to the challenges affecting foreign investors in South Sudan?

Appendix three: Research Budget

Activities	Unit	Cost per unit Cost (SSP)	Total Cost (SSP)
Transport cost within Juba	1	20,000.00	20,000.00
Research Equipment & Materials			
Cell Phone	1	130,000.00	130,000.00
Mobile internet Modem	1	15,000.00	15,000.00
Laptop Computer	1	250,000.00	250,000.00
Anti- Virus Software	1	5,000.00	5,000.00
Cell phone usage charges	1	3,500.00	3,500.00
Meetings & Refreshment	1	65,000.00	62,000.00
Paper, Pens, markers	1	1,000.00	1,000.00
Publication and Dissemination		300,0000	300,000
Printing/photocopying of Questionnaires	100	200	20,000.00
Research Assistant			
Printing/Photocopying of Thesis	3	3,000.00	9,000.00
Binding of Thesis	3	5,000.00	5,000.00
Total expenses			820,500.00

Appendix four: Work Plan

Activity Description	Proposed Deadline	Remarks
Research Proposal Development	12 th -26 th July 2022	
Submission of the Research Proposal	27 th July-12 th Aug 2022	
Review and Resubmission	18 th -30 th August 2022	
Proposal Development	20 th -	
Field Research	17 th -31 October2022	
Data Analysis and drafting of Section 4 & 5	1 st -25 th Nov. 2022	
Review and Final Submission	28 th Nov -9 th December 2022	

Appendix Five: Approval Letter for Data Collection from the Ministry of Finance and Planning

UNIVERSITY OF JUBA

School of Social
and Economic Studies
(SSES)

P.O. Box 82 Juba
South Sudan

UJ/SSES/20.J.1

Date: 5/12/2022

To whom it may concern
Post Graduate Studies

Subject: Student's Research Project

As an essential requirement for the award of the Master Degree in Economics

University of Juba, each student is required to carry out research project and to submit thereafter.

Student Name: A. Kay Maker Nyuon Under Index No: 2020-MSC-041

has shown interest to undertake research study on The Impact of Government Expenditure on Economic growth in South Sudan.

In this context, the School of Social and Economic Studies administration is kindly requesting your esteemed office to permit the above-mentioned student to undertake his study with your assistance by providing him/her with information to realize this academic objective

Please accept our highest assurance.

Thanks

Dr. Abraham Kuol Nyuon
Dean, School of Social and Economic Studies
University of Juba

Cc: Deputy Vice Chancellor for Academic Affairs

Cc: Registrar, SSES

Cc:

Cc: File

Appendix Six: Approval Letter for Data Collection from the National Revenue Authority

UNIVERSITY OF JUBA

School of Social
and Economic Studies
(SSES)

P.O. Box 82 Juba
South Sudan

UJ/SSES/20.J.1

Date: 8/12/2022

To whom it may concern
Post Graduate Studies

Subject: Student's Research Project

As an essential requirement for the award of the Master Degree in Economics

..... University of Juba, each student is required to carry out research project and to submit thereafter.

Student Name: AKau Maker Nyuon Under Index No: 2020-MSC-04

has shown interest to undertake research study on The Impact of Government Expenditure on Economic growth in South Sudan.

In this context, the School of Social and Economic Studies administration is kindly requesting your esteemed office to permit the above-mentioned student to undertake his study with your assistance by providing him/her with information to realize this academic objective

Please accept our highest assurance.

Thanks

Dr. Abraham Kuol Nyuon
Dean, School of Social and Economic Studies
University of Juba

Cc: Deputy Vice Chancellor for Academic Affairs

Cc: Registrar, SSES

Cc:

Cc: File

Appendix Seven: Approval Letter for Data Collection from the Bank of South Sudan

BANK OF SOUTH SUDAN (BOSS) HUMAN RESOURCES DEPARTMENT

Date 21st December 2022

To: **Dr. Abraham Kuol Nyuon**
Dean, School of Social and Academic Affairs
University of Juba

SUBJECT: RE- REQUEST FOR DATA COLLECTION

Reference to your letter dated 8th December 2022 requesting Bank of South Sudan to facilitate data collection to your student **Mr. Akau Maker Nyuon** under index number **20-MSC-04** in final year.

The bank has rendered every assistance so required, and therefore, this letter serves to inform your esteemed office that, **Mr. Akau Maker** has completed collection of his research and is being sent back to your end to continue with his research paper.

Best regards

21 DEC 2022

David Manyon Nak 21/12/2022

David Manyon Nak
Director of Human Resources For
BOSS-Juba

Cc: File